

Oxo-molybdenum (V) Complexes

R. L. Dutta and B. Chatterji

The co-ordination chemistry of lower-valent molybdenum, especially of the +5 oxidation states, is one of current interest¹⁻⁴. In so far as the results have been interpreted, the magnetic moment has been diagnostic of the monomeric or polymeric nature of the complexes. Polymerisation is revealed in a low magnetic moment for the complex, whereas the near-spin-only value indicates monomeric nature.

As part of the programme of studies on the complexes of oxo-metal cations⁵⁻⁶, chelates of oxo-molybdenum(v) with a variety of nitrogen-donor ligands are under our active investigation. The results so far obtained have warranted this preliminary communication.

Using $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ as the source of molybdenum(v) and by varying solvents and other reaction conditions, several complexes with quinoline-2-carboxylic acid (QH), quinoline-8-carboxylic acid(Q'H), pyridine 2-carboxylic acid(PicH), benzohydroxamic acid (BH_2), *N*-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine (RH), and 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene (TH) have been synthesised in a pure, crystalline form and characterised through elemental analysis (Table I). In most cases, the valence states have been determined through oxidation by ferric alum or ceric sulphate. No spin-only value has been so far recorded for the magnetic moment, instead a few have turned out to be diamagnetic. In terms of prevalent opinion on the subject, most of our complexes are polymeric. Unfortunately, no suitable solvent has been found for an assessment of the molecular size of the complexes.

TABLE I
Oxo-molybdenum(v) complexes.

Compound.	Found.	Calc.	Colour.	Oxidation state.	Magnetic moment (B.M.).
1. $[\text{MoOClQ}_2] \cdot 0.5\text{HCl}$	Mo : 19.32% N : 5.80 Cl : 10.60	18.83% 5.50 10.40	Deep chocolate	+5	0.73
2. $[\text{MoO}(\text{OH})\text{Q}_2]$	Mo : 19.92 N : 5.88	20.40 5.90	Deep orange	+5	Diamagnetic
3. $[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q.Py}]$	Mo : 25.20 N : 7.60	25.20 7.30	Orange-red	+5	Do

1. Mitchell and Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 4570.
2. Mitchell, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 963; 1964, **26**, 1967.
3. Bailin and Jonassen, *ibid.*, 1963, **25**, 99.
4. Horner and Tyree, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 122.
5. Dutta and Lahiry, *this Journal*, 1961, **38**, 1001; 1962, **39**, 871; 1963, **40**, 53, 67, 857; 1964, **41**, 62, 546.
6. Dutta and Ghosh, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, in press.

TABLE I (contd.)

Compound.	Found.	Calc.	Colour.	Oxidation state.	Magnetic moment (B.M.).
4. $[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q} \cdot \frac{1}{2} (o\text{-phen})]$	Mo : 23.90% N : 7.15	24.40% 7.10	Deep chocolate	+5	0.2
5. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{Pic}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	Mo : 36.22 N : 5.90	36.02 5.70	Orange	..	Diamagnetic
6. $[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q}']$	Mo : 32.20 N : 4.80	32.20 4.67	Light orange	+5	Not measured
7. $[\text{MoO}(\text{OH})(\text{BH})_2]$	Mo : 23.54 N : 6.94	23.94 7.00	Greenish yellow	Not determined	1.27
8. $[\text{MoO}(\text{OH})(\text{R})_2]$	Mo : 17.68 N : 5.07	17.30 5.06	Yellow	Not determined	Diamagnetic
9. $[\text{MoO}_2\text{T}] \cdot 2.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Mo : 25.05 N : 11.22 H ₂ O : 11.93	25.00 10.90 11.68	Amber	Not determined	Not measured

Work is progressing with a variety of other nitrogen-donor ligands. A full description of the results including preparation, characterisation, magnetic and spectral studies will appear at a later date. We intend to extend these studies to Mo (III) as well.

The authors wish to thank Mr. N. N. Ghosh of the University College of Science, Calcutta, for permitting them to work on the Gouy magnetic balance.